

PREDICTION OF NUMBER OF COVID-19 AFFECTED PERSONS BY USING GOMPERTZ CURVES

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Abstract: This paper aims to analyze the First and the Second COVID-19 Waves experienced by India, using the modified versions of Gompertz Curve (MGC) and to estimate the maximum number of affected individuals for each wave with the best possible accuracy. The period of collected data is from 30th January 2020 to 11th July 2021. The entire dataset is segregated into two parts, i.e., for the First and the Second Waves, and then modelled individually using the MGC. The robustness of the fits is checked, and then residuals are further modelled successively to improve the accuracy of the estimates. The accuracy in the predictions is overwhelming. Finally, a comparative analysis of the results has been performed with the Logistic Model and the ARIMA Models. The present model gives much better prediction and it is found to be robust in the sense that even with initial 30 to 40 observations it predicts the ultimate number of affected individuals quite accurately which enables the Government to take timely actions.

Keywords: COVID-19, Disease modelling, Gompertz curve, Forecasting, Fractal analysis

1. Introduction

Analytical research on COVID-19 can be primarily subdivided into two parts. A substantial amount of literature has focussed on proposing models for robust estimation of the daily infections while the other has tried to model the cumulative number of infections. Since the two objectives and the estimation procedures are different, these two models are unlikely to give identical results and hence need to be studied separately. Economists, statisticians, epidemiologists, and computer scientists have employed distinct methods for predicting COVID-19 as accurately as possible. Given these two broad categories of existing work, the present paper shall attempt to cater to the second, by implementing the Gompertz Curves. However, the objective of the paper is not only to pointwise map out the trajectory of cumulative infections, but try to estimate the “maximum” number of infections that can occur in a particular wave. An early and accurate overall estimate of the maximum possible infections will result in a further efficient allocation of the scarce healthcare resources and make the battle against COVID-19 more effective.

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For modelling daily cases, the R^2 can be used as a goodness of fit measure, whereas, for cumulative data, it is more meaningful to measure goodness of fit through the prediction error of the ultimate cumulated frequency. Note that the models used for short-run predictions cannot be used for catering to the long-term objectives as mentioned above. However, our model can be easily used for obtaining the short-run predictions of the daily cases from the cumulative predictions. This is clearly an additional advantage of the modelling technique illustrated in this paper.

The paper is divided into the following sections considering the above background. Section 2 deals with the literature review. Section 3 highlights some key properties of the Gompertz Curves. Section 4 provides the econometric analysis. In Section 5, we present the Perturbation Analysis and Section 6 serves as a conclusion and provides a detailed summary of the findings.

2. Literature Review

Apart from research being undertaken in the domain of vaccination, drug therapy, and other clinical aspects, considerable research has also been carried out on patients who have recovered and on patients with co-morbidities. A thorough analysis has been performed based on the people who recovered to shed some light on how to deal with the active cases. The Gompertz Curve, often interpreted as the “natural growth curve” has found its way into many such contemporary studies. Some of the examples are as follows.

2.1. Existing Literature on the application of the Gompertz Curves

Mazuruk and Nenickova (2020) used the Gompertz Curve to model the COVID-19 cases of USA and applied it to the data on COVID-19 deaths. They inferred that in both cases, the Gompertz Curve was able to provide a reasonably good approximation to the data. Mendieta et al. (2020) also provided a similar conclusion from their analysis on Italy, Spain, and Cuba. They applied the Logistic curve and the Gompertz Curve and showed that, for these countries, the Gompertz model had better estimates for the peak in confirmed cases and deaths. Rypdal and Rypdal (2020) made a detailed comparison of epidemic curves for Sweden and Norway using the Gompertz curves and they too observed that the epidemic curves for COVID-19-related deaths for most countries with a reliable reporting system are surprisingly well described by the Gompertz growth model. They also suggest that countries with rapid initial growth and slow later decay can be modelled satisfactorily using the Gompertz function.

2.2. Studies on India and the Indian Subcontinent

In the Indian context, Gupta and Kumar (2020) used exploratory data analysis to report the situation for the period of January to March 2020 and used the ARIMA model to predict future trends. They inferred that a huge surge in the number of COVID-19 positive cases was predicted in April and May 2020. The average was forecasted to be approximately 7000 patients in a total span of 30 days in April 2020. A further enhanced study on India was done by Pandey et al. (2020). They used regression models for forecasting. According to them, cases were expected to rise to about 5000 in a two-week period. Also, Tak et al. (2020) used the dataset from 11th March to 25th June 2020 to fit the ARIMA model. The model with minimum AIC was used for forecasting. The predicted root-mean-square-error (Pred-RMSE) and base root mean square error (Base-RMSE) were used to validate the model. To validate the model, the dataset was distributed into a training set and a validation set. The training dataset from 11th March 2020 to 4th June 2020 was used to fit the model and for estimation of parameters and data from 5th June 2020 to 25th June 2020 was used to validate the model. The ARIMA (1,3,2) and ARIMA (3,3,1) models fit best for cumulative cases and deaths.

Maan et al. (2022) implemented the ARIMA Model to predict the Third Wave of COVID-19 for India. They used the daily data about the number of COVID-19 reported cases and deaths till 30th August 2021. The ratio of training to test data set was 4:1. During the week of August 23-29, 2021, there was a gradual increase in the number of daily cases reported across the country. It was predicted that this trend may continue, and the number of reported cases can rise till December 2021. Yousaf et al. (2020) used the cumulative data to predict the number of cases in Pakistan from 26th February to 12th April, 2020 to forecast the number of cases, deaths, and recoveries for the upcoming month. Results from the model revealed that the number of confirmed cases shows a rapid exponential growth which may increase by 2.7 times compared to the reported cases until the end of May 2020. Similarly, the forecast model for recoveries showed an exponential growth. The model revealed that the number of recoveries would possibly increase by 8 times at the end of May 2020. Aslam et al. (2021) used the ARIMA Model to perform a comparative study of India, Bangladesh and Pakistan and predicted the growing number of cases for 14 days starting on 1st July 2020 and ending on 14th July 2020. The 14-day forecast for the three countries showed that the number of cases will grow steadily in Pakistan and India but will remain constant in Bangladesh.

Ghosh et al. (2020) took a unique approach to forecasting COVID-19 infections in India. They considered the state-wise data of infections and modelled them using the logistic and exponential curves. They inferred that the predictions from one model might be misleading and hence suggested a linear combination of the exponential and logistic curves for the purpose of realistic predictions. Khan et al. (2021) have implemented the machine learning techniques of Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine, and Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) algorithm to project the number of cases for India using the data set available as of 10th June 2020.¹ The model performance was evaluated using the value of the coefficient of determination (R^2), mean square error (MSE), root mean square error (RMSE), and mean absolute error (MAE). The authors showed that the confirmed number of cases would start declining from the first week of August. From the curve, it showed that the daily new confirmed cases would start declining at the end of July 2020 if the conditions remain the same in the country.

We now turn to the literature on implementation of the epidemiological models for studying COVID-19 which is the benchmark in the study of epidemic modelling. Bedi et al. (2020) proposed a modified Susceptible-Exposed-Infected-Recovered-Deceased (SEIRD) model for projecting COVID-19 infections in India and its five states having the highest number of total cases namely Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Delhi. In this model, the exposed

¹ Gaussian process regression (GPR) is a non-parametric, Bayesian approach to regression, which is widely used in the area of machine learning. A significant benefit of GPR is that it can work well on small datasets and have the ability to provide uncertainty measurements on the required predictions. GPR taking exponential kernel function was used in forecasting considering the worst-case scenario. Exponential GPR is identical to the Squared Exponential GPR except that the Euclidean distance is not squared. Exponential GPR replaces inner products of basis functions with kernels slower than the Squared Exponential GPR. The Exponential GPR handles smooth functions well with minimal errors.

A support vector machine is a supervised learning algorithm that can be used for classification or regression. An SVM classifies data by finding the best hyperplane that separates data points of one class from points of the other class. SVM contains linear, quadratic, cubic, fine gaussian medium gaussian, coarse gaussian SVM for classification and predictions. The quadratic SVM has medium model flexibility, hard interpretability, and it uses binary medium and large multiclass for memory usage. Decision trees are easy to interpret, fast for fitting and predictions and, low on memory usage. It contains a coarse tree, medium tree, fine tree to increase the model flexibility with the maximum number of splits settings.

compartment contained individuals who may be asymptomatic. The values of these parameters of the model have been estimated in this paper through curve fitting to actual data. The optimized values of these parameters have been obtained by the minimize function. This function used dual annealing method for obtaining a global optimal solution. The effect of different lockdowns imposed by the Indian government has also been used in modelling and analysis in the proposed Modified SEIRD model. Deep Learning based Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model has also been used by Bedi et al. (2020) to perform short-term projections. The projections obtained from the proposed Modified SEIRD model were compared with the projections made by LSTM for the next 30 days. Data upto 15th August 2020 has been used for carrying out the predictions.

The results obtained from the Modified SEIRD Model for India confirmed a peak of COVID-19 cases for India on 3rd November 2021 with 8,57,390 daily cases, and the disease may die out towards the end of 2023. The short-term projections were performed using the proposed Modified SEIRD model as well as the LSTM model for India and its five worst-affected states for the next 30 days, i.e., from 16th August 2020 to 14th September 2020. The values of the Recovery Rate calculated by both models are very close to the Actual Recovery Rate values on 15th August 2020 in the selected states. However, a contrasting trend in the values of Case Fatality Rates can be observed for Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka, where one model predicts a hike but the other indicates a decline in the value.

We note here that the Gompertz Curve is yet to be applied to analyse the COVID-19 situation of India. The present paper attempts to fill this gap. Note that since the objective of our paper differs from those of the existing literature, our results are not directly comparable with the results of the stated papers. Although there is no gainsaying that a pointwise mapping of the COVID-19 spread is necessary, however given the huge population that needs to be catered to through relief measures, it seldom becomes a compulsion to make early and accurate measurement. Any such prediction shall offer multifaceted benefits in raising a timely alarm for a country to prepare itself and take measures to tap the onset of another probable COVID-19 wave.

3. The Gompertz Curves

Gompertz Curves have nowadays gained ample popularity for modelling economic and biological phenomena and particularly as epidemic curves. As the objective of our paper is to use the Gompertz Curve for modelling cumulative COVID-19 cases of India, the present section highlights some of the important mathematical properties of this curve.

For practical purposes, we consider the Gompertz Curve as:

$$y = e^{a-bc^{-ct}} \text{ where } a, b, c > 0 \quad \dots(1)$$

Throughout the paper we will define:

y = cumulative frequency of daily infections,

N = Maximum cumulative frequency that can be attained (e^a) i.e the asymptote,

b is the displacement on the x-axis and c is the growth rate.

So, essentially, b and c are the shape parameters.

The following are the desirable properties of the Gompertz Curve for such an analysis:

3.1. Property 1

Equation (1) can also be extended to construct a generalized version of the Gompertz Curve as:

$$y = e^{a-bc^{f(t)}} \text{ where } a, b > 0,$$

where $f(t) = c_1 t + c_2 t^2 + c_p t^p$, is a p th degree polynomial in time ($p \geq 1$).

Hence, we consider our Generalized Gompertz Curve as:

$$y = e^{a-bc_1t+c_2t^2+c_3t^3}, a, b > 0 \tag{2}$$

For the generalized Gompertz Curve also $N = e^a$ provided $c_3 < 0$.

3.2. Property 2

Statistically, we can say that in general the sum, or the average, of several Gompertz curves will not be a Gompertz curve, just as several logistics do not, in theory, give a logistic when added or when averaged. But it has been found in practice that the sum of a number of logistics does in fact often approximate closely a logistic as shown by Reed and Pearl (1927), Winsor (1932) comments that it will be true that Gompertz curves will often add to give something very close to a Gompertz curve.

4. The Econometric Analysis

The data used in this paper pertains to the daily cumulative number of COVID-19 infections in the country from 30th January 2020 to 11th July 2021 (529 data points), covering both the first and the second waves. To begin with our analysis, we first plot the data over time as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Daily Cumulative Infections over Time

The cumulative number of daily infections should follow a sigmoid shape. However, due to two major variants of COVID-19 acting at different time periods, we observed two COVID-19 waves each having the expected sigmoid shape. Thus, analysis of the two waves cannot be done together and hence there arises a need to split our datasets into two parts for the first and the second waves, respectively. Scientifically, it has not been possible to demarcate a well-defined cut-off point for marking the end of the first wave and the beginning of the second wave. Hence, to proceed with the analysis, we had to subjectively decide on the cut-off points based on the above plot.

Since the curve fairly flattens in the interval, i.e., from 300 to 400, the cut-off point lies in this interval. We omit some observations from this range for the purpose of brevity and fix the duration of the two waves as follows:

First Wave: 1st March 2020 to 31st January 2021; Time: [32, 368]; having 337 data points,

Second Wave: 12th February 2021 to 2nd July 2021; Time: [380, 520]; having 141 data points.

We can now fit the Gompertz Curves to the first and the second waves separately. For the purpose of demonstrating the modelling technique, in the following Sections, we shall be only focusing on the First Wave of COVID-19 in India. Similar results can be obtained for the Second Wave as well.

4.1. Analysis of the First Wave

With the subjectively determined cutoff points, we can fit either of the following curves to the data as discussed in Section 3. Further, given the flexibilities of the Gompertz Curves, we also suggest the following modification:

We modify the Gompertz Curve as:

$$y = d + e^{a-bc^{-ct}} \dots(3)$$

And the Generalized Gompertz Curve can be modified as:

$$y = d + e^{a-bc_1t+c_2t^2+c_3t^3} \dots(4)$$

Note that from henceforth, we shall be referring to this curve as the Modified Gompertz Curve (MGC). Theoretically, the term ‘d’ appears as a “drift”. However, before proceeding further, it is important to know how we can interpret ‘d’ empirically.

Firstly, as $t \rightarrow \infty$, we get $y = y_{max} = d + e^a$. Thus, it is something like a correction to the maximum number of persons who will be affected. Our motivation behind suggesting this modification can be summarized as follows:

- Intuitively, it is evident that in the initial days of the onset of this new infection, the number of reported cases were very small and even close to zero per day.
- Secondly, being a new infection, it may have been misreported.
- Also, according to the ICMR, the specificity of the *real-time reverse transcription–polymerase chain reaction* (RT-PCR) test is not 100%. Hence, chances of false negatives cannot be ruled out.

Besides these, there might have been a plethora of other scientific and non-scientific reasons which make the data of the first few days at the onset of the first wave extremely unreliable. However, within a few weeks, with the imposition of lockdown and other social restrictions, testing took place and the number of infections began to be reported more accurately. Hence, we will include this correction factor to have a model-driven approach in order to have a closer approximation of the real picture. The Gompertz Curves, being a non-linear function of time and non-linear in its parameters, we need to apply non-linear regression for fitting the curve to the data (Gujarati et al., 2021). However, to begin with non-linear least squares, we first need to obtain initial starting values of our parameters.

We get the initial estimates by using the following linearized model. To illustrate the steps, we use the Gompertz Curve (with d).

$$\begin{aligned}
 y &= d + e^{a-bc^{-ct}} \\
 \ln(y - d) &= a - bc^{-ct} \\
 \ln(a - \ln(y - d)) &= \ln b - ct \\
 \ln(\bar{a} - \ln(y - \bar{d})) &= b^* + c^* t \dots(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, with known \bar{a} and \bar{d} we can obtain $b = e^{b^*}$ and $c = -c^*$

Similarly, the expression for the Modified Gompertz Curve becomes:

$$\ln(\bar{a} - \ln(y - \bar{d})) = b^* + c_1 t + c_2 t^2 + c_3 t^3 \dots(6)$$

Hence, with known \bar{a} and \bar{d} we can obtain $b = e^{b^*}$, c_1 , c_2 , c_3 .

For obtaining the starting values of a , d we proceed in the following way:

- Since we do not start from the zero point i.e., the lower asymptote of the curve is not zero, we initialize $d = \bar{d}$ with the cumulative infections on the first day (as chosen by the authors) of the wave.
- For a , we know $y_{\max} = d + e^a$. From the dataset, this can be taken as the cumulative number of infections on the last day of the wave. We increment this by 20% and initialize a as $\bar{a} = \ln(1.2 y_{\max} - \bar{d})$.

We will now use the method of nonlinear least squares for fitting the curves by plugging these initial estimates. Hence, the four models under our consideration are:

- The Gompertz Curve: $y = e^{a-bc^{-ct}}$
- The Shifted Gompertz Curve (with d): $y = d + e^{a-bc^{-ct}}$
- The Generalized Gompertz Curve: $y = e^{a-bc_1t + c_2t^2 + c_3t^3}$
- The Modified Gompertz Curve: $y = d + e^{a-bc_1t + c_2t^2 + c_3t^3}$

Which model will fit better is decided on the basis of $\hat{\sigma}$ (the standard error of regression adjusted for degrees of freedom) and the AIC values as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Fitted Models for the First Wave

Sl. No.	Model	(Residual s.e.)	AIC value
1	Gompertz Curve	105400	8756.313
2	Gompertz Curve (with d)	91720	8663.828
3	Generalized Gompertz Curve	80621	8432.30
4	Modified Gompertz Curve	57340	8349.172

Thus, it is evident that the suggested modifications improved the goodness of fit dramatically (as confirmed by the lower $\hat{\sigma}$ and the AIC values for both the cases). Hence from the above discussion, we can infer that the Modified Gompertz Curve (MGC) seems to be the most suitable fit to the data of the first wave as confirmed by both $\hat{\sigma}$ and the AIC values. To investigate further, we look at the residual plot from the MGC Fit shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Residual Plot for the First Wave

Clearly the residuals have a cyclic pattern. Hence, the Fractal Analysis has been used for residual analysis. Further details of the residual analysis have been provided in the Appendix.

5. The Perturbation Analysis

Section 4 gives enough evidence that the suggested modification has enhanced the model fit. However, there might be a concern over that fact that the modification enhancing the fit might simply come out due to the choice of the cut-off points that have been used for determining the first and second waves. Hence, in this section, we try to study the robustness of this modification as described by the MGC. In order to do this, we proceed through the following steps:

- We try to modify the length of the first and the second waves by changing the starting points of the waves in a systematic way by changing it by 5 days in either direction. For our purpose, we choose our cut-off modifying vector as
- We now want to check if the maximum number of cumulative infections in either of the waves is nearly immune to slight changes in our consideration of the cut-off points.
- From our dataset, we know the actual maximum number of cumulative infections. We now wish to obtain the fitted value of the maximum cumulative infections by modifying the starting days and obtaining the fits in each case.
- We will then compare to see how close the fitted values in each case are to the actual number of cumulative cases.

5.1. Perturbation Analysis for the First Wave

Note that the actual cumulative cases on the 368th day is 10757610. In our analysis in the previous section, we had considered the starting point as Hence, the set of starting cut-off points under consideration are: .

Table 2: Perturbation Results for the First Wave

Sl. No.	Starting Cut-off Point	Predicted Maximum Cumulative Cases	Error Percentage
1	27	10695200	0.58%
2	32	10695828	0.57%
3	37	10696186	0.57%
4	42	10696246	0.57%

Thus, our observations as summarized in Table 2 confirm that subjective determination of cut-off has negligible impact on the estimates for the first wave. One can show that the same is true for second wave as well.

6. Discussion and Conclusions

The study confirms that the Gompertz Curves can be used as a reasonably appropriate tool for modelling the covid situation of India. A seemingly important observation that comes out from the Perturbation Analysis that the slight changes in the cut-off points for the waves do not have much effect on the resulting estimates and thus need not be so precise. Further, refinements can also be made by modelling the residuals through the Fractal Analysis.

However, the fact that the current analysis using the Gompertz Curves outperforms the other methods used in the literature can only be validated via a comparative analysis of the Gompertz Curves with the others. Given, the voluminous amount of literature on COVID-19, the two most

widely used modelling techniques have been the ARIMA and the Logistic Models.

So, what follows next is comparing the results of these two models with that of Gompertz Model used here. For this purpose, we refer to Tak et al. (2020) for comparison with ARIMA and Khan et al. (2021) for comparing with the Logistic Model. A natural criticism that might come is that the results from Gompertz curve might turn out to be better on the account of more data that has been used for analysis. Hence, to do away with this and the other heterogeneities, the results of the Gompertz Curves are compared by fitting the model over the same time period as that taken by the corresponding authors and comparing the results via their criteria.

6.1. Comparing the Gompertz Curves and the ARIMA Model

Tak et al. (2020) used the data on cumulative infections from 11th March 2020 to 25th June 2020 to fit the ARIMA model. The ARIMA (1,3,2) model was the best fit for cumulative cases. The predicted root mean square error (Pred-RMSE) was used to validate the model with forecasts for the next 10 days. So, if we denote the training dataset as: , then the Pred-RMSE for the forecast of the next 10 days is computed as:

$$PredRMSE = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{10} \frac{(y_{n+j} - \hat{y}_{n+j})^2}{10}}$$

The model with the lower Pred-RMSE gives better forecasts. Our results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of ARIMA Model and the Modified Gompertz Fit

Criterion	ARIMA (1,3,2)	Modified Gompertz Fit
Pred-RMSE	21137	19464.73

We note that, even with this limited data, the results from the Modified Gompertz Fit is better. Note that here the residual analysis could not be carried out, as the residuals have turned out to be non-stationary; yet the above results indicate higher prediction accuracy for the Modified Gompertz Fit.

6.2. Comparing the Gompertz Fit with the Logistic Model

Khan et al. (2021) used the data set available as of 10th June 2020 and provided forecasts for the next two months (60 days). The authors have implemented the ML models as mentioned in Section II and went on to compare the results with that of the Logistic Model proposed by Batista (2020) given by $y = \frac{a}{1 + be^{-ct}}$.

The model performance coefficient of determination (R^2), mean square error (MSE), root mean square error (RMSE), and mean absolute error (MAE), where

$$R^2 = \text{corr}^2(Y, \hat{Y}), \text{ where } \hat{Y} \text{ is the predicted value.}$$

The Modified Gompertz model in this case is fitted to the data till 10th June 2020 and the results are compared. Note that, here also, residual modelling has not been used, as the residuals turned out to be non-stationary which is confirmed confirmed by the ADF Test. Table 4 summarizes our results.

Table 4: Comparison of Logistic Model and the Modified Gompertz Fit

Criterion	Logistic Model	Modified Gompertz Fit
R^2	0.857	0.995
Pred-RMSE	704456.9	173029

Hence, here also, the Modified Gompertz Fit provides better prediction accuracy as compared to the Logistic Model. Incorporating this inference in future research is expected to make a meaningful contribution, especially for modelling any new wave that India might face in the future.

Ghosh et al. (2020) further point out that, as extensive testing may not be feasible given India's large population, the logistic and exponential fits may lead to under-forecasting or over-forecasting. Given that the modification to the Gompertz curve suggested in this paper has been introduced to address these unaccountable factors, it becomes evident that we have been able to employ a better model to analyse the pandemic. However, there are some limitations in the study. For example, we have not included non-medical interventions like lockdowns or quarantines in the proposed model. The proposed model is based on reported cumulative COVID-19 cases. The quality of COVID-19 infection reporting is a known problem due to various factors like the under-reporting of COVID-19 cases may have influenced our results in this study. We have introduced a correct factor "d" to account for this. However, further extensive techniques can be explored to address the issue of under-reporting. This can be seen as a possible extension of the present work.

The methodology discussed in this paper is significant because it helps tackle not only the medical aspect of the COVID-19 crisis but also the problems on the economic front through predictive modelling. Given the limited healthcare resources that are available, especially for vastly populated countries like India, often early decisions need to be taken regarding the efficient allocation of these resources for any COVID-19-like pandemics in the future. Hence, it is recommended and indeed empirically more relevant to use the Gompertz curves for intensity prediction, especially when our objective is to study the epidemic curves.

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APPENDIX

The Residual Analysis

In Section 5, we observe that the residuals from the Modified Gompertz fit as obtained from both the waves show some cyclical fluctuations. Hence in order to model these, we implement the frequency domain approach of the time series analysis where we model cyclical fluctuations through appropriate sine or cosine fits. Let us suppose that we model any variable exhibiting cyclical fluctuations as:

$$Y_i = A \cos(2\pi\omega_i t + \phi) + \epsilon_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots(7)$$

Here, ω_i denotes the principal frequency of the fitted curve and ϕ denotes the phase. Note that we will always have $\omega_i \leq 0.5$. The time period of the fitted wave is defined as $T = 1/\omega$. However, we cannot fit the curve (7) directly to the data and hence we proceed in the following way.

$$Y_i = (A \cos \phi) \cos(2\pi\omega t) + (-A \sin \phi) \sin(2\pi\omega t) + \epsilon_i$$

$$Y_i = \beta_1 \cos(2\pi\omega t) + \beta_2 \sin(2\pi\omega t) + \epsilon_i \quad \dots(8)$$

Hence, now the model is linear in parameters, and we can apply the OLS method to fit (8) to the residuals.

Residual Analysis of the First Wave

Before proceeding with the residual modelling technique discussed above, we will first check the stationary of the residuals using the ADF Test. The residuals are stationary as confirmed by the augmented Dickey-Fuller test p-value = 0.01 < 0.05.

We now resort to the spectral analysis to proceed further in this section. We now want to obtain the frequency levels that have contributed to the observed cyclical patterns in the residuals. Hence we now plot the periodogram to obtain the principal frequency(s) as shown in Figure A1.

Figure A1: Scaled Periodogram for the Residuals from the First Wave

The principal frequency is obtained as: $\omega_1 = 0.008902077$; Time period= 112.33 days. We try to fit the model to the first residuals:

$$r_t = \beta_1 \cos(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \beta_2 \sin(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \epsilon_t \quad \dots(9)$$

By running this regression, we obtain the estimates of $\hat{\beta}_1$ and $\hat{\beta}_2$. Using these estimates as the initial values, we now try to fit the curve using nonlinear LS method for all the parameters below:

$$y = d + e^{a-b\epsilon_1 t + c_2 t^2 + c_3 t^3} + \beta_1 \cos(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \beta_2 \sin(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \epsilon_t \quad \dots(10)$$

However, on plotting the residuals obtained from fitting (9), the residuals still have a cyclical pattern (with lower magnitudes), and hence we suspect the presence of fractals. We now move on with modelling the residual of residuals as follows. Here, we will now fit the model:

$$rr_t = \beta_3 \cos(2\pi\omega_2 t) + \beta_4 \sin(2\pi\omega_2 t) + \epsilon_t \quad \dots(11)$$

where the second principal frequency is obtained as:

$$\omega_2 = 0.01186944; \text{Time period} = 84.25 \text{ days.}$$

Now, for the fractal analysis, we take the ratio $k = \frac{\omega_1}{\omega_2} = 1.33$. And then we try to fit the following model:

$$y = d + e^{a-b\epsilon_1 t + c_2 t^2 + c_3 t^3} + \beta_1 \cos(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \beta_2 \sin(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \beta_3 \cos(2\pi k\omega_1 t) + \beta_4 \sin(2\pi k\omega_1 t) + \epsilon_t$$

Here, we want to check whether k is also significant or not. Then we further attempt to enhance our fractal analysis by trying to include the squared and cube components of k . The initial estimates of the β are obtained by successive residual modelling and then we will use these to perform non-linear least squares for fitting the Gompertz+ Residual fits. A summary of the residual analysis of the first wave is presented in Table A1.

Table A1: Summary of the Residual Analysis for the First Wave

Residual Number	Frequency	Time period	Amplitude
1	0.008902077	112.33 days	54559.36
2	0.01186944	84.25 days	38213.83
3	0.01780415	56.1667 days	24256
4	0.0148368	67.4 days	23823.01

We now consider our four models as:

Fit 1 is: $y = d + e^{a-b\epsilon_1 t + c_2 t^2 + c_3 t^3} + \beta_1 \cos(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \beta_2 \sin(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \epsilon_t$

Fit 2 is:

$$y = d + e^{a-b\epsilon_1 t + c_2 t^2 + c_3 t^3} + \beta_1 \cos(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \beta_2 \sin(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \beta_3 \cos(2\pi k\omega_1 t) + \beta_4 \sin(2\pi k\omega_1 t) + \epsilon_t$$

Fit 3 is: $y = d + e^{a-b\epsilon_1 t + c_2 t^2 + c_3 t^3} + \beta_1 \cos(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \beta_2 \sin(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \beta_3 \cos(2\pi k\omega_1 t) + \beta_4 \sin(2\pi k\omega_1 t) + \beta_5 \cos(2\pi k^2\omega_1 t) + \beta_6 \sin(2\pi k^2\omega_1 t) + \epsilon_t$

Fit 4 is:

$$y = d + e^{a-b\epsilon_1 t + c_2 t^2 + c_3 t^3} + \beta_1 \cos(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \beta_2 \sin(2\pi\omega_1 t) + \beta_3 \cos(2\pi k\omega_1 t) + \beta_4 \sin(2\pi k\omega_1 t) + \beta_5 \cos(2\pi k^2\omega_1 t) + \beta_6 \sin(2\pi k^2\omega_1 t) + \beta_7 \cos(2\pi k^3\omega_1 t) + \beta_8 \sin(2\pi k^3\omega_1 t) + \epsilon_t$$

The results are summarized in Table A2. We can infer that the Fractal assumption seems to be correct and all the modified curves are better fit to the data as indicated by the consecutive decrease of $\hat{\sigma}$ and the AIC values for the first wave. An interesting point worth noting is that extending the fractal analysis to include the k and k^2 terms had led to a commendable lowering of $\hat{\sigma}$ and thereby giving a clear indication of the fourfold improvement in the fit. However, this sharp descend of $\hat{\sigma}$ somewhat dampened when the k^3 term is also included. Hence, we do not proceed any further as it indicates towards the possibility of the presence of an unwanted noise variable which might lead to

absurd results if k^4 and higher powers are included. One can also confirm that modelling the second COVID-19 Wave also yields similar results.

Table A2: Fitted “Gompertz + Residual” Models for the First Wave

Sl. No.	Model	$\hat{\sigma}$ (Residual s.e.)	AIC value
1	Modified Gompertz Curve	57340	8349.172
2	Fit 1	40090	8109.930
3	Fit 2	29530	7906.836
4	Fit 3	14560	7431.923
5	Fit 4	12170	7313.361